

Horizon Europe project DEEP PPU

RF Generator of the Power Propulsion Unit

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To convert the DC electrical power from the spacecraft into the high DC voltage levels and the high frequency AC voltage required to operate the ion thruster, a power processing unit (PPU) is used. One of the components of the PPU is the radio frequency generator (RFG), which is used to ionize the propellant allowing to control the thrust. The RFG architecture is shown in the following figure, where a DC/DC stage controls the power and the DC/AC stage is resonant inverter that synchronizes with the load's frequency and phase to ensure a high efficiency power transfer.

Buck converter operating in Triangular Current Mode:

In order to minimize the size of the DC/DC converter, high frequency operation (200kHz-500kHz) is required, being necessary the use of GaN semiconductors and to operate with Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) to reduce switching losses. The proposed topology, Buck converter operating in Triangular Current Mode, allows for ZVS operation under the whole range, being necessary the use of Digital Control to face the control challenges of the topology. The following picture shows the block diagram of the DC/DC state.

The DC/DC converter has been built and tested at full power in open loop, achieving very high efficiency 98.7% efficiency at 1kW. Currently, the converter is being tested in closed loop operation. The following pictures show the prototype as well as measurements that validate the proposed design.

Picture of the DC/DC prototype

Main waveforms operating at 1kW with ZVS

Temperature of high side GaN switch at 1kW

Closed loop operation: output voltage step

Resonant Inverter for the RF Generator:

The main blocks of the RFG inverter are shown in the following figure.

The proposed solution has been tested at full power (1kW) in closed loop, being self-synchronized the inverter with the load. Therefore, the proposed concept has been fully proven, achieving in the inverter very high efficiency at full load: 97% at 1kW and 700kHz.

The modelling and design of the harness is very challenging since it operates at 700kHz. One of the next steps is to test the inverter with a real harness to operate under the desired conditions.

The following pictures shown the RFG inverter prototype and different measurements that validate the proposed concept in closed loop and at full power.

Picture of the setup to test the inverter

Main waveforms operating at 1kW and 700kHz with ZVS

Temperature of high side GaN switches at 1kW

Harness effect on the admittance seen by the RFG inverter

About project

The DEEP-PPU consortium will develop a disruptive Power Processing Unit for medium and high-power GIT. The project is a natural continuation of GIESEPP-MP, where a first step has been taken to develop a power supply for the screen grid and integrate it within the current PPU design for ArianeGroup RIT-2X thruster. The activity is focused on the improvement and optimization of the power electronics as one of the major cost drivers of an electric propulsion system, in particular for gridded ion technology.

Project consortium

DEEP-PPU team is composed of 6 organisations. Each of the partners is responsible for a specific work package or task within the project. Most of the partners have worked together before. Project coordinator - Airbus Crisa.

Airbus Crisa

Airbus Crisa
Project coordinator & PPU
www.crisa.es

AIRBUS

Airbus DS
Responsible for / definition of space specific requirements
www.airbus.com

Polytechnic University of Madrid Centro de Electrónica Industrial
Responsible for Radiofrequency Generator electronics
www.cei.upm.es

AXON CABLE
Responsible for interconnection of systems / Manufacturer for space harness assemblies
www.axon-cable.com

WIT Berry
Responsible for communication and dissemination activities
www.witberry.eu

Fraza
Responsible for expertise in magnetics design
www.fraza.si

Competitive advantages proposed by DEEP-PPU

DEEP PPU team's proposed solutions stands out with significant mass and cost reduction compared to the existing solutions on the market. It aims to strengthen the EU's space sector competitiveness in the international market and secure the autonomy of supply for critical technologies and equipment.

50%
Cost reduction

30%
Mass and volume reduction

The integration of the RFG unit within the PPU

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